

residue, (1.0 g) remained, after distilling off the solvent, washed with ether, was found to be unreacted polymer while ethereal washings afforded *p*-toluidine (1.80 g.).

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Estimation of Free Sulphur by Amperometry

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ONE of the most widely used method for the determination of free sulphur in vulcanized rubber is the sulphite method originally developed by Bolotnikov and Gurova¹. The method is based

on the reaction between sulphur and an aqueous solution of sodium sulphite to form sodium thiosulphate which is estimated by volumetric titration with standardized iodine after removing the unreacted excess sodium sulphite with formalin. Sulphur-bearing accelerators interfered with the results and Oldham, Baker and Craytor² modified the method so that it remains valid in presence of the common accelerators like mercaptobenzothiazole (MBT) by precipitating out the latter as cadmium salt before carrying out the titration of the thiosulphate. The method recommended by ASTM³ is based on Oldham's modification. In the present paper we investigated the suitability of the amperometric titration method for the estimation of the thiosulphate formed from sulphur under the above experimental conditions.

The procedure of Oldham *et al.*² was followed except for the titration step. Known amounts of sulphur (6 mg downwards) were boiled with 100 ml of 5% sodium sulphite solution for 2 hr in presence of 5 ml of 1% sodium stearate suspension and 1 g of paraffin wax. 100 ml of 0.5% strontium chloride were then added to precipitate fatty acids followed by 10 ml of 3% cadmium acetate to precipitate mercaptobenzothiazole which might be present in the actual rubber vulcanizate. In other words the experimental conditions were maintained exactly the same as in the actual analysis of rubber vulcanizates. The solution was then filtered into a 500 ml volumetric flask and treated with 5 ml of 40% formalin solution and 12 ml of glacial acetic acid. The volume was then made upto the mark and 50 ml aliquots were taken for amperometric titration of the thiosulphate with iodine using a rotating platinum wire electrode and a standard saturated calomel electrode. The results are reported in Table 1.

TABLE I—AMPEROMETRIC ESTIMATION OF SULPHUR BY
SULPHITE DIGESTION USING IODINE SOLUTION

Sulphur taken (mg)	Strength of iodine soln. used	Sulphur found (mg)	Deviation (%)
6.046	$0.464 \times 10^{-2}N$	6.054	+0.13
6.046	"	6.069	+0.21
3.032	"	3.034	+0.06
3.032	"	3.034	+0.06
0.302	$0.464 \times 10^{-3}N$	0.298	-1.32
0.302	"	0.299	-0.99
0.151	"	0.141	-6.60
0.151	"	0.141	-6.60

It can be seen that free sulphur can be estimated very accurately even when present in amounts as low as 3×10^{-4} g by amperometric titration of the thiosulphate formed by sulphite digestion. Vogel⁴ has recommended the use of a supporting electrolyte which is 0.1 M in potassium chloride and 0.004 M in potassium iodide for amperometric titration of thiosulphate with iodine. We have found that this

is not necessary, since the same result is obtained whether there is any potassium chloride present or not.

In a stock containing Rubber 100, Zinc oxide 5, Stearic Acid 2, Sulfur 3, Accelerator 1, Antioxidant 1, the free sulfur value falls below 0.002 g. per one gram sample of the vulcanizate towards the end of vulcanization. Amperometric titration method will thus be more suitable for estimating such low concentrations of sulphur than the volumetric method of titration. We have actually found that the volumetric method gives reliable results upto about 0.005 g. of sulphur, below which the method is quite inapplicable as it becomes increasingly difficult to establish the endpoint. Moreover, the amperometric method is faster and does not require cooling of the reaction medium as is the case with the volumetric procedure². Further, the above results show that the presence of the different reagents added to the reaction medium for various purposes (such as for precipitating the accelerators which may be present in the rubber vulcanizates), does not interfere in the amperometric titration. Thus the amperometric method should be preferable for the estimation of free sulphur in rubber vulcanizates by the sulphite digestion procedure.

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Occurrence of Chemical Reaction in the Intermediate Zone during Electrolysis

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THE classical Hittorf mechanism clearly rules out any kind of change, not even a change of concentration in the intermediate zone during electrolysis. Though this is generally tacitly assumed to be true, we cite here some examples where such a tenet is clearly of no applicability.

Change of Concentration in the Intermediate Zone: This is best seen during electrolysis of a dichromate solution in a W-tube (Fig. 1). The tube is filled with a potassium dichromate solution ($N/20$ to $N/40$) and

a current of about 10 mA, is sent through the solution. In the course of about three hours a sharp boundary between a light coloured alkaline chromate solution and a deep coloured reddish brown chromic acid solution appears at B. Now if the current is still continued for overnight or so, another sharp boundary appears at B' and the portion BB' eventually becomes

Fig. 1

completely colourless and neutral. This is in clear violation of Hittorf principle as the current here brings about a fall in concentration in the intermediate zone in preference to the cathode zone (CB) and/or the anode zone (AB'). This happens with practically all electrolytes but is spectacularly shown by Cr(VI) and many dye solutions¹.

Chemical Reaction in the Intermediate Zone: That the intermediate zone can be a seat of reaction can be easily demonstrated by the experiment described below. The cell shown in Fig. 2 is filled with $N/1000$ solution of any electrolyte say, sodium chloride or sodium sulphate. The central limb M is filled with some benzene under nitrogen in which is dissolved a dye, say, chry-soidine. On sending a small current of say, 1 mA. through the two platinum foil electrodes it would be seen that the dye solution gets slowly decolorised, more than half being decolorised in a couple of days or so. Not only the dye gets decolorised but simultaneously the benzene layer becomes a strong seat of chemical reaction as seen by the fact that hydrogen and oxygen gets continuously liberated at the rate of about a ml per day in the intermediate zone M. These gases can be identified by withdrawal and analysis of the gas in M through the stopcock S from time to time. In any case some gas has to be let out